

METHODOLOGY OF LEARNING LAW

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Annotation. To date, a wealth of experience has been accumulated in the field of legal education, which makes it possible to state the existence of multivariate concepts of legal education. Under legal education, we mean the process of purposeful transfer of knowledge, skills and the formation of stable skills in the field of legal reality, which allow us not only to have theoretical ideas about certain legal norms of life, the laws of the country, but also to apply this knowledge in practice.

Keywords: theory, approach, situation, law, time

In the IV century. BC e. higher education in Athens. Even then, they started talking about the lecture form of education, which makes it possible to transfer knowledge from a teacher to his students. Famous philosophers for a fee taught those who wished (in the form of lectures or conversations) the art of eloquence, logic and the history of philosophy. The most important indicator of the high level of development of ancient Greek culture was the emergence of science among the Greeks. At the end of the 8th century BC. in Miletus, a whole scientific school arose, which is usually called the Ionian natural philosophy. Its representatives - Thales, Anaximander of Miletus, Anaximenes for the first time thought about what is the root cause of the world. So, Thales suggested that water is the basis of everything on Earth, and Anaximenes is air. Centuries have passed... Lectures and seminars are gradually becoming the leading forms of study at universities. The lecture-seminar system of education (it is also called coursework) is well known to teachers since the 13th-14th centuries, when the first universities appeared in Europe - the main form of education in higher educational institutions. Despite the ongoing criticism, disputes about the purpose and place of the lecture-seminar system, especially lectures in the system of higher education, this system is just as tenacious as a lesson in secondary school and in basic vocational education. The lecture and seminar system is designed for a high level of intellectual development of students and is distinguished by a greater degree of student independence. At the same time, the lecture-seminar system has many similarities with the class-lesson system: - permanent study groups include students who are approximately the same in age and level of preparedness (for lectures, homogeneous groups are combined into streams); A variation of the lecture-seminar (course) system is the subject-course system of education, which is most often used in part-time and part-time

education. It involves such an organization of the educational process, in which the disciplines of the curriculum and the corresponding final tests and exams are distributed according to the years of study (courses) in compliance with continuity, and tests and exams within the same course are taken by pupils and students as they are individually prepared. On the basis of this system, higher correspondence education is most often organized, as well as education in evening (open) general education schools. Abroad (USA, England, etc.), the so-called "virtual universities", "virtual colleges", etc., are widely used. These are network associations (consortiums) of universities, colleges, etc., providing opportunities for the student to study simultaneously in several educational institutions on the basis of a distributed (combined) curriculum. At the same time, all educational institutions that are members of the consortium mutually recognize all exams and tests passed by students in any of the institutions that are members of the consortium. Obviously, in the future, such virtual educational institutions should soon appear in Russia. The literature presents a classification of forms of work in the learning process according to learning systems (a learning system can be defined as a mechanism for organizing learning within an integral educational program - primary education, general secondary education, secondary vocational education, etc.).

Independent study work is the highest form of learning activity (just like self-study). A. Diesterweg wrote: "Development and education cannot be given or communicated to any person. Anyone who wishes to partake of them must achieve this by his own activity, his own strength, his own exertion. From the outside, he can only receive excitement ... ". Independent work is defined as an individual or collective learning activity carried out without the direct guidance of a teacher, but according to his instructions and under his control. According to the forms of organization, independent work can be frontal - students perform the same task, for example, write an essay; group - to complete training tasks, students are divided into groups (3-6 people each); steam room - for example, when conducting observations under a microscope, in the classroom in a language laboratory; individual - each student performs a separate task, for example, writes an essay on a given topic. Independent work can take place in the classroom, audience (laboratory, office, workshop, etc.), during extra-curricular and extracurricular activities (at the school experimental site, in the corner of wildlife, on excursions, etc.), at home. The most common types of independent work: work with a textbook, reference books or primary sources, problem solving, exercises, essays, presentations, term papers and theses,

observations, laboratory classes, experimental work, design, modeling, etc. The authors pay special attention to the Teaching with the help of a teacher (teachers). In turn, teaching (learning) with the help of teachers can be divided (classified) into individualized learning systems and collective systems. Various lectures are traditional in the system of higher professional legal education. Scientists-teachers distinguish the following types of lectures: informational, problematic, lecture-visualization, a lecture for two, a lecture with pre-planned errors, a lecture-press conference. Information lecture. Its signs are well known. Having historically developed as a way of transferring ready-made knowledge to students through a monologue, a lecture under the influence of a changing, developing content of training and education cannot remain the same, informational. Problem lecture. In it, the process of cognition of students approaches search, research activities. Lecture-visualization. This is the result of a search for new opportunities for implementing the principle of visibility known in didactics, the content of which changes under the influence of data from psychological and pedagogical science, forms and methods of active learning. Lecture together. The dynamism of the problematic content of the educational material is carried out in a live dialogical communication between two teachers. Lecture with pre-planned mistakes. It largely satisfies the need to develop students' skills to quickly analyze professional situations, act as experts, opponents, reviewers, and isolate incorrect or inaccurate information. Lecture-press conference. It is close to the corresponding form of professional activity with the following changes. Having named the topic of the lecture, the teacher asks the students to ask him questions in writing on this topic.

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